

USAGE OF NONLINEAR FINITE BEAM ELEMENTS IN ROTOR BLADE MODELS FOR LOAD CALCULATIONS OF WIND TURBINES

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Summary

The most important structural part of a wind turbine model used for load calculations is the rotor blade. Commonly, rotor blade models are generated by a modal reduction of a parametrized finite beam element model to one or several modal reduced parts. The dynamic behavior of these models is limited to the mode shapes at the operating point of modal reduction. It introduces an undesired behavior at different operation conditions.

To overcome this, we implemented nonlinear finite beam elements into the wind turbine simulation software *alaska/Wind*. On the basis of a reference blade model and a 65m long Nordex blade we validate this blade model to other tools and measurements. We demonstrate that an efficient solver yields a practicable computation time and introduce an anisotropic damping model for finite beam elements, which is compared to measurements.

1. Introduction

One of the main components of wind turbines are rotor blades. As the blades get slender and more flexible, the correct representation of aeroelastic interactions in simulation models gets more and more important.

A method of generating rotor blade models using nonlinear finite beam elements is presented. This approach in combination with an efficient solver [1] yields load calculations with high grade of approximation of the physics.

2. Simulation Model

The presented simulation results of wind turbines were obtained using the software *alaska/Wind*. It combines the general purpose multibody dynamics software *alaska* with an aerodynamics library including widely used industrial standard approaches (i.e. BEM with respective wake models, dynamic stall models etc.).

The basis of all blade model descriptions is the parametrization of cross sections at selected positions along the blade axis. This data is used to parametrize a fully structural coupled FE beam model according to the Timoshenko theory.

Fig. 2.1 Blade model parametrization

For load calculations the blade model is usually created by modal reduction of one or several blade parts.

Fig. 2.2 Modal reduced blade models

However, the dynamic behavior is correctly represented for only one operating state – the state of modal reduction.

A nonlinear blade model instead fulfills this for all operating states. Therefore, we implemented a nonlinear beam element model in *alaska/wind*, which can be used also for load calculations. Thus, the maximal possible functionality – with the given blade beam model description – is enabled by avoiding the modal reduction.

Fig. 2.3 Nonlinear beam element model

In most operating points, the displacements and the eigenfrequencies of a modal reduced blade are close to the nonlinear blade model, which is solved in every time step. However, the dynamic reaction differs for certain directions. E.g., this can be observed shortly before rated wind speed, when the blade has a large flap deflection. Especially the torsional rotation within the edge modes is poorly represented. This behavior is illustrated in the next section in figures 3.2 and 3.3.

3. Model Validation

As validation of the implemented nonlinear beam elements a 86m long blade based on the DTU 10MW reference wind turbine from [2] was modeled within the FEM software ANSYS using the nonlinear beam element BEAM188 (ANSYS), in *alaska/Wind* with the new beam elements (FE) and as modal reduced blade (MR). The modal reduced blade consists of seven modes (three edge, three flap and one torsional mode) and quadratic modes (quadratic modes correct the greatest difference between linear and nonlinear beams by introducing a nonlinear coupling of bending and extensional degree of freedom using a quadratic approach). All three models use the same cross section parametrization for the beams including extensional and torsional stiffness,

coordinates for center of mass, elastic center and shear center. For all three blade models the mass properties are exactly the same in the three main directions x, y, z:

total mass	41738 kg		
center of mass	26.14 m	-0.12 m	-0.36 m
princ. inertia in kgm ²	151644	1.7244e7	1.7276e7

For further examination a linearization of the three blade models at a static equilibrium was performed at two operating points: under no load and under a constant rotation at 5 rpm.

The eigenfrequencies of all models are very close:

	no load			at 5 rpm		
	ANSYS	FE	MR	ANSYS	FE	MR
1	0.614	0.614	0.614	0.625	0.625	0.625
2	0.938	0.938	0.938	0.940	0.944	0.940
3	1.746	1.746	1.746	1.757	1.757	1.758
4	2.763	2.762	2.761	2.769	2.769	2.767
5	3.584	3.583	3.583	3.594	3.593	3.594
6	5.687	5.678	5.678	5.694	5.686	5.684
7	6.037	6.035	-	6.047	6.044	-
8	6.614	6.617	6.618	6.608	6.612	6.618

The mode shapes of the blades for the non-deflected state and at the operating point of 5 rpm are very close for all models. Since there is only the centrifugal force as load, the deflections stay very small and also the modal reduced blade yields a good result – such that there is almost no visible difference in the mode shape components flap, edge and torsion for all lower modes. Figure 3.1 exemplarily shows the edge and flap deflections as well as the torsional rotation over the blade for the second edge mode. The largest deflection is scaled to one and all other deflections are scaled respectively.

Fig. 3.1 Mode shape of 2nd edge mode at 5rpm for DTU 10MW blade

Further, this result shows a very good agreement of the beam models in alaska/Wind and ANSYS.

For all subsequent illustrations and validations of the nonlinear beam elements a model of a 65m long Nordex blade is used. It is discretized by 60 beam elements, which are parametrized by mass properties, several stiffnesses and coordinates of cross section points (shear center, mass center and elastic center). The modal reduced blade includes seven modes (three flap, three edge and one torsional mode) and quadratic modes.

In reality the rotor blades go through a variety of operating points. Starting with almost no deflection while idling, it increases to a high flap deflection shortly before rated wind speed. With increasing wind speed the flap deflection reduces as the blade gets pitched.

To illustrate the dynamic behavior of the modal reduced blade model we use a turbine model including the 65m long blade. A constant wind speed of 7m/s has been set and a stationary state has been reached setting appropriate conditions (i.e. no gravitational load, no tilt and cone angle, no wind shear etc.). The induced wind has been calculated using a BEM method.

The mode shapes at this operating point show a good agreement of flap and edge deflections, but a wrong coupling of bending and torsion within the modal reduced blade (see figures 3.2 and 3.3). Especially the edge modes (see Fig. 3.2) exhibit a torsional rotation, which is generally too large and points into the wrong direction at certain parts of the blade. This is critical as the coupling of bending and torsion may determine the stability of the blade behavior.

Fig 3.2 Mode shape of 1st edge mode at a wind speed of 7m/s for Nordex NR65 blade

Fig 3.3 Mode shape of 1st flap mode at a wind speed of 7m/s for Nordex NR65 blade

For further validation, the displacements of the 65 meter long blade, measured at a test rig, are successfully used to validate the alaska/Wind beam model results.

Fig. 3.4 Static blade test at test rig, Nordex Energy GmbH, Rostock

Fig 3.5 Nordex NR65 blade deflections of blade models and test results

With an increasing number of considered nonlinear effects in the simulation models, the deviation to the measurements decreases.

4. Usage in Turbine Development

The nonlinear blade model is increasingly used at Nordex for load calculations, because significant load differences for certain design load cases compared to the modal reduced blade model could be observed. The nonlinear finite elements add stiff differential equations to the simulation model.

Explicit and semi-implicit solvers, used for simulation models with modal reduced flexible bodies, get very inefficient in this case. Therefore, a generalized-alpha solver was implemented, see [1]. While the degree of freedom increases from less than 40 (modal reduced) to more than 1000 (nonlinear beams), the computation time increases only by a factor of 6 to 10 – depending on the model complexity. This allows the usage in development projects.

Due to the improved bend-torsion coupling within the nonlinear blade model, reliable stability analyses can be realized. Edgewise blade modes are known to be weakly damped because of their low aerodynamic damping, especially, for long, slender blades, if the edgewise blade motion couples with torsional blade motion [3,4]. It is important to accurately assess the stability limits and the order of magnitude of blade oscillations in the design process.

In field studies on a N131/3000 prototype the edgewise blade oscillation level between measurement and simulation has been compared. The simulation has been done with the multibody system dynamics tool alaska/Wind. The 65 meter long blades are discretized as described above. The Rayleigh damping coefficient was adapted to meet the measured structural damping. Unsteady aerodynamic effects (dynamic stall) were included in the simulation. In Figure 4.1 the bandpass-filtered 1st and 2nd maximum edgewise blade-root moments in a ten minute time series are compared between measurement and simulation under normal production. The measured trend is captured well by the simulation.

Fig. 4.1 Bandpass-filtered edgewise moments

5. Damping approach

For a modal reduced blade the commonly applied modal damping method yields a very easy and successful way to adjust the simulation model to measured damping values. This feature gets lost when the modal reduction to more than one part is used – as the one-to-one correspondence of real mode shapes and modes of the modal reduced part gets lost. Within the theory of nonlinear finite elements, the commonly used Rayleigh damping does not yield a reasonable method for adjusting the necessary structural blade damping.

To make the beam model most practicable we implement a reasonable damping approach. A method, which respects direction-dependent damping in a stiffness proportional and mass proportional way, inspired by the ideas in [5], is chosen.

The approach is implemented as an inner damping model. To parametrize the anisotropic damping each beam element carries four parameters for stiffness proportional damping and four parameters for mass proportional damping. Two parameters act in the principal directions of mass inertias or bending stiffness, whereas the other two act in extensional and torsional direction.

This approach enables the user to obtain a good match between lower flap and edge modes as well as a torsional damping behavior, which is enhanced compared to constant stiffness proportional damping. As common blades use a coupling of bending and twist, the locally defined damping in bending directions already generates some torsional damping. Thus, the torsional damping may not be independently parametrizable. The following figure shows an optimally configured damping for the 65m long blade.

Fig. 5.1 Measured damping and anisotropic damping of nonlinear beam model for Nordex NR65 blade

The damping of the first two flap and edge modes correspond to the measurements. The higher bending modes show a higher damping, due to the dominating stiffness proportional damping in this region. The torsional damping is higher as in the measurement, but much better as in a constant stiffness proportional damping method.

6. References

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